

Texts to Treasures: The Lived Experiences of English Teachers Employing Multimodal Approach in Literature Classes

Riodel A. Antolin

Abstract. This study investigated the implementation of the multimodal approach in literature instruction by English teachers, focusing on their experiences, strategies, and insights derived from this pedagogical method. Employing a qualitative research design, in-depth interviews were conducted with ten English teachers from Davao del Norte. The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis, identifying two primary themes for the English teachers lived experiences: transformative instruction and learner responsiveness. These themes illuminate how the multimodal approach fosters deeper student engagement and enriches literary learning. The strategies employed by teachers included adaptive strategies, multimodal techniques, and inclusive practices, underscoring their innovative responses to diverse learning needs. Additionally, the study highlights reflective growth and sustainable innovation as key outcomes, demonstrating how the approach contributes to professional development and long-term instructional improvement. In light of these findings, it is recommended that educators and educational institutions promote the multimodal approach in literature classes, as it facilitates dynamic, inclusive, and meaningful learning experiences for students.

KEY WORDS

1. Multimodal approach, 2. literature 3. English teachers

Date Received: April 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: May 15, 2025 — Date Published: June 18, 2025

1. Introduction

The multimodal approach is a teaching and learning methodology that integrates multiple modes of communication—such as text, visuals, gestures, audio, spatial arrangements, and digital media—to enhance meaning-making and engagement. However, operating in this new paradigm is not without problems. Teachers often wrestle with the appropriate balance between designing multimedia lessons and ensuring academic rigor with critical engagement with literature. Also, teachers face the critical task of balancing the creative, media-rich approach with the traditionally rigorous de-

mands of literary analysis. Globally, teachers face diverse struggles with integrating multimodal techniques into literature instruction. In Malaysia, for instance, teachers report difficulties in balancing the use of multimodal texts with the development of students' analytical and creative skills. Teachers felt confident in designing lessons that effectively integrate multimodal strategies, largely due to a lack of institutional support and inadequate training (Kummin et al., 2020). In Chile, preservice teachers established that active users in a nonacademic context will do the same in school due to resource and curric-

ula misalignments (Farías Veliz, 2019). Meanwhile, Jiang et al., (2020) in China highlighted how an EFL teacher had incorporated digital multimodal composing (DMC) into teaching. It is discovered that the educator now started to see herself not just as a teacher, but even as a good mentor and peer model—extending her job and boosting student motivation, even in the face of unorganized exams and institutional mandate. Simultaneously, in USA, Smith et al., (2021) worked with English language learner 10th-grade students and learned multimodal units of English literature from digital media. The effect observed was dramatic as they learned a better grasp of the material, could clarify literary meaning more effectively, and had more fun than otherwise—testimony to the very powerful role of imaginative creativity and visual storytelling in second-language learning. In the Philippines, recent inquiry continue to sing the same crisis that has haunted the earlier studies: while multimodal literacies of teaching literature hold promising enrichments, teachers in the public and private schools both face insurmountable barriers. In 2023, Caramay et al. (2023) corroborated that English literature teachers, especially from private schools, were struggling to adapt to virtual classrooms, citing matters like preparation of multimodal tasks, coordination of platforms and learning outcomes, and re-acclimatizing assessment criteria. But once adjusted, the teachers stated that digital multimodality turned classrooms into interactive, innovative, and student-focused environments and hence encouraged critical thinking in addition to better participation. Meanwhile, a report on teachers of public schools, Barcleona et al. (2024) documented exactly the same issues: lack of materials, lack of pedagogical training, and time deficiency. But the very same instructors were super-resourceful, always using personal resources or community inputs to finance multimodal and experience-based learning methods. These first-hand accounts trace

a steady line: notwithstanding structural limitations, Filipino instructors keep finding new and creative means of making multimodal literature instruction relevant and meaningful. In the same light, a multimodal approach to teaching literature has also reached the local scene. It initiate that this approach to literature not only improved literary comprehension but also encouraged students to express their interpretations creatively, bridging cultural gaps and fostering a more inclusive learning environment. Salinas (2020) emphasizes the need for educators in Mindanao to adopt multimodal strategies to reflect the region’s rich cultural heritage and meet the varied learning preferences of students. Despite its potential, English teachers face several challenges in employing the multimodal approach, including the limited access to resources in Sto. Tomas West District. Although related studies address multimodal teaching strategies, there is a scarcity of research focusing on the lived experiences of English teachers in employing the approach in literature class. For instance, Lim and Tan-Chia (2023) analyzed multimodal learning within a theoretical framework but focused on broad educational settings rather than literature-specific context. Lachica (2023) ESL teachers in the Philippines and showed how post-pandemic movement towards multimodal pedagogy introduced real challenges—like limited budget, vibrant technology, and being forced to restructure study material. Despite that, teachers depicted adaptability through being more resilient, innovative, and responsive to students’ need. Moreover, this study aims to fill this gap by exploring the lived experiences of English teachers in Sto. Tomas West District. Beyond its academic contributions, the study holds significant social relevance as it seeks to inform stakeholders on how to better support teachers in adopting multimodal strategies. Taking into consideration the cited problem situation, I found it timely to conduct this study. This brought the necessity

to conduct an inquiry about the multimodal approach of English teachers in literature classes as well as values that are deemed necessary and useful. I hope that this study enlightens the identified sectors of the academe. This includes the educational leaders, school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders can benefit from the findings of this study because it can provide them with insights and valuable lessons regarding the state of the delivery of instruction pertaining to literature, especially those that are used for the multimodal approach. Also, they can utilize the results and find ways to better enhance and support the teachers to be efficient and effective in delivering multimodal approach in teaching literature. This may include providing access to diverse media platforms, interactive e-books, learning management systems, or applications that allow the students to explore various forms

of media. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals to be aware and informed about the multimodal approach employed by the teachers and find ways to offer some help, guidance, tools, and assistance to them. They may provide regular training for teachers in crafting interactive learning materials. The teachers can benefit from this study by looking into the findings and learnings from the multimodal approach taken from the perspective of other teachers. The stakeholders may provide better support to enhance the delivery of a multimodal approach to the literature of the teachers. Finally, this would be helpful to future researchers as an additional contribution to their references for future research in the field of multimodal approach and literature teaching and how it is remolding the way we deal with diversity and deliver learning in classrooms.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study investigates and analyzes the experiences and strategies utilized by English teachers in Davao del Norte as they endeavor to enhance their multimodal approach to teaching literature. The study provides useful insights into the practices of teachers during their literature lessons. In the end, the study increases my understanding of how to effectively utilize a multimodal approach in order to cater to the learning needs of each individual student and to improve their literary skills and understanding. The central objective of this data collection revolved around capturing the real-life experiences of English teachers as they utilize a multimodal approach in teaching literature. The outcomes of this phenomenological study would provide me with a deeper understanding of the precise multimodal approach that teachers employ to improve the literary skills and understanding of students. Furthermore, I would assess the efficacy of these strategies in elevating the literary skills of the students. The valuable insights obtained from this study possess the potential to exert a positive influence on various aspects of inclusive education, language education and teaching, professional development initiatives, and educational policies aimed at cultivating empowering and supportive learning environments within classrooms.

1.2. Research Questions—This study explores the experiences and strategies of English teachers on a multimodal approach to literature. The research is carried out with the purpose of addressing the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of English teachers regarding the multimodal approach in teaching literature?
- (2) What strategies do English teachers use to implement a multimodal approach in teaching literature?
- (3) What lessons are learned from the findings of the study?

1.3. Significance of the Study—This study holds significant value for various stakeholders in the field of education, particularly in enhancing the teaching and learning of literature through innovative methods. By exploring the lived experiences and strategies of English teachers in implementing a multimodal approach, the study provides valuable insights into how diverse modes of communication—such as visual, auditory, spatial, and digital texts—can enrich literary understanding and student engagement. It contributes to the growing body of knowledge that supports the integration of multimodal teaching in English classrooms.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of this study was anchored on the on Jerome Bruner (1961) Constructivism Theory. As cited by Ouzzine et al., (2022), the main theme inherent in Constructivism is that people learn by constructing new ideas and concepts by interpreting them through comparison with previous knowledge. People attribute meaning to new ideas, and this process represents learning. This implies that learning is not about simply being exposed to new information but is an active process whereby learners examine, code, decode, and interpret new concepts and ideas. Learners select and transform information, construct “hypotheses,” and rely on cognitive structures to build and refine their schemas. As applied in the context of the study, the Constructivism Theory explains how students process what they have learned to be able to interpret it (Chand, 2024). It also postulates that students are not passive in this process, instead they are actively processing what they have learned, selecting, transforming, and constructing their own version. In a literature class using a multimodal approach, students can showcase their understanding of the lesson through various media. This gives them the freedom to interpret and process what they have learned. The study is further reinforced by the Multiliteracies Theory by New Group London (1994, as cited in Drewry et al., 2019). Multiliteracies is a pedagogical approach developed by the New London Group (NLG) that aims to make classroom teaching more inclusive of cultural, linguistic, communicative, and technological diversity. According to the NLG, a multiliteracies pedagogy accepts and encourages a wide range of linguistic, cultural, communicative, and technological perspectives and tools being used to help students better prepare for a rapidly changing, globalized world. Multiliteracies are related to multimodality, as many modes are encouraged to be used in different forms of expression. In the context of the present study, the Multiliteracies Theory postulated inclusivity and diversity in delivering instruction and showcasing learning. In order to continue helping students have the widest range of opportunities possible in creating their lives and contributing to their community and to their future, schools now adapt to the growing availability of new technologies for teaching and learning, communication channels, and increased access to cultural and linguistic diversity. Thus, this theory helps the researcher understand how the multimodal approach reshapes and enhances the ways teaching and learning literature can be delivered. Drawing on the New London Group, authors underscore the fact that pedagogy of multiliteracies goes beyond traditional literacy to multimodal forms of meaning-making, including visual, auditory, spatial, gestural, and digital literacies. The review highlights the relevance of multiliteracies in facilitating inclusive and culturally responsive pedagogy through support for diverse student backgrounds, learning styles, and communication practices (Hong and Tan, 2020).

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addressed the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explained the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study’s implementation. Moreover, it offered thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concluded by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions—*

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions—*A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions were vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions formed the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions established the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical found-

ations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Asmawi et al., 2024). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study.

Ontology This section of the study focused on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Poucher et al., (2019), ontology can be defined as the study of the nature of reality. The authors also assert that the research participants’ perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. In connection with that, the present study recognized the complexity of the experiences of the English teach-

ers regarding the multimodal approach since they taught in different schools with different classroom set-up. Also, the study recognized the diversity of their strategies for different literary pieces. With this, every teacher's story added to a wide range yet collective understanding of their experiences and strategies. It is my sole responsibility to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of the experiences, strategies, and lessons that teachers had in employing a multimodal approach in their literature classes.

Epistemology Epistemology dealt with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Tunstall et al., (2022), the researcher made an effort to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I became an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced collection of data. This approach supports the gathering of firsthand experiences and strategies, which were critical in exploring the subjective realities of the participants. In this respect, I, myself interviewed the participants and gathered firsthand their experiences and strategies for employing a multimodal approach in teaching literature.

Axiology It concerned the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Sirris (2022), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study is crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process (Peddle 2022). As a researcher, I handled each participant's narrative with care and integrity. This commitment guaranteed that the experiences and strategies of English teachers in employing a multimodal approach, with care and integrity, and I had the utmost respect for the information they provide were communicated truthfully, mirroring both their individual and research values. Method-

ology According to Crotty (2020), this is "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This study explored the experiences and strategies of English teachers in employing a multimodal approach to teaching literature using a qualitative methodology. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, certain techniques like focus groups and in-depth interviews were employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories (Maher 2025). These techniques were chosen because they could successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences.

Rhetoric In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions in order to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Rochma, 2025). I utilized an engaging and respectful narrative style that honored the voices of the participants while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only made the research easier to read but also guaranteed that the interpretations were strong and based on the experiences of the participants.

Qualitative Assumptions Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal was to explore the experiences and strategies of English teachers in employing a multimodal approach to teaching literature in Davao del Norte. My objective is to gather information about their experiences, strategies, and lessons in relation to the phenomenon I was studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals in the field of teaching literature, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of

their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I supported a level of investigation that goes beyond cursory observations. My research aimed to investigate the experiences, strategies, and lessons learned by teachers upon employing a multimodal approach to teaching literature. I emphasized the significance of understanding the complexities of human experience in light of the various perspectives that are shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal his-

2.3. Design and Procedure—The study utilized a qualitative research approach, specifically a phenomenological inquiry to discover and understand the lived experiences of English teachers in employing multimodal approach in literature classes. According Gautam et al., (2023) qualitative research is a sort of social activity that examines how people interpret and make sense of their own experiences in order to comprehend their own social reality. To gather, evaluate, and interpret data from visual and textual sources, as well as oral history, researchers used interviews, diaries, notebooks, classroom observations and immersions, as well as open-ended inquiries. Moreover, Hwang et al., (2021) said to be exploratory in nature, with the goal of figuring out the "how and why" a particular social occurrence, or strategy, that works in a given background. The purpose was to understand the social reality where we live and why things are the way they are. A qualitative research design was used in this study to have a rich, thick, and detailed description on the realities of English teachers in integrating multimodal approach in literature class. I wanted to explore the lived experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of English teachers in their teaching effectiveness, professional growth, and integration of diverse approach that made students engaged and develop their multiliteracy skills. On the other hand, the phenomenological inquiry was used

(Neubauer et al., 2019). To capture the profound and complex nature of the multimodal approach, my study placed a strong emphasis on in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives. I hoped to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the experiences, challenges, strategies, and lessons related to the multimodal approach all while upholding phenomenological principles.

in this research in which McLeod (2023) mentioned that the phenomenological approach investigates human events through the words of the people involved. "Lived" experiences are what they're called. The goal of phenomenological research is to describe the importance of each subject's experiences. Such type of research is utilized to look into situations where there isn't much information available. Mathews (2023) also added by clearly showing rather than hiding the research participants' personal realities, perceptions, and convictions, motivations a deed, and wisdom, and approaches in phenomenological nature are more effective in describing rather than explaining personal experiences. Interpretation element added to the research's relevance and significance through investigating societal structures, policies, and practices from the participants' personal views, which were clearly visible in the research. In this study, a phenomenological study was used in my research as I wanted to grasp more about the understanding of the realities and common experiences of English teachers in employing multimodal approach in literature class. Such method and approach helped me know about the experiences and challenges the English teachers faced. Also, in-depth interviews are suited for my study to obtain specific evidence on a certain phenomenon. Moreover, I made use of purposive sampling on my participants' selection. After all the data were gathered, a the-

matic analysis was done to find patterns of significance in the data that could be used to answer the research issue at hand. To further support this, according to Tavakol et al., (2025), a phenomenological study is a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations

of a particular phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations (Shorey Ng 2022). Therefore, my goal is to identify a phenomenon that revolved around the participants' experience with employing a multimodal approach to teaching literature. I collected information from people who had direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998, as cited in Owusu Sarfo et al., 2022) recommends 5 to twenty-five 25. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample

size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002 as cited in Mocănasu, 2020). The participants of this study were ten (10) English teachers from Davao del Norte. The participants were selected based on the following criteria: they must be teachers for three years or more, they must handle English subjects, have employed a multimodal approach in their literature class, and be willing to participate in the study. Moreover, purposive sampling was used in the selection of the participants. Purposeful sampling, as defined by Shaheen et al., (2019), is a sampling strategy used by qualitative researchers to identify people who can provide them with a wealth of knowledge about their research topic. This entails locating or selecting a group of people who are well-versed in and have encountered the phenomenon in question.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were crucial because they related to the moral principles and guidelines that governed my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carried out my investigations responsibly, treating participants with respect and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhered to established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik,

2020).

Social Value

The expected benefits that could justify human research included direct benefits to research participants as well as societal benefits, sometimes known as social value. One of the reasons for conducting this study was its societal importance. This study aimed to add to the body of research on the realities of the English teachers employing multimodal approach in literature class. Further, the findings of this

study could form the basis for policy recommendations as well as the development of relevant trainings and workshops for English teachers. Likewise, the results can inform strategies to enhance learning environment, align teaching practices with 21st-century competencies, and ultimately contribute to the holistic development of students in Sto. Tomas West District.

Informed Consent Informed consent forms were important to obtain to protect researcher participants' rights in research studies. They ensure transparency, build trust, and established a clear understanding between researchers and participants. Moreover, they outlined the study's purpose, procedures, potentials risks, and participants' rights. Before the actual interview, the researcher obtained informed consent from the participants. In this study, the researcher explained to participants about the complete procedure of the study, the aims and purposes of the investigation, and the various dimensions of ethical concerns in order to gain their approval and thoroughly convince them to be a participant in the study. The researcher also notified the study's participants that their contribution is entirely intentional and that they could opt out of the study at any moment. They were also informed as to their significant contribution in the success of this research endeavors.

Vulnerability of Research Participants The participants were regarded as susceptible because they may have been emotionally influenced by the interview guide questions. The researcher, however, ensured that the interview schedule was clear of offensive words. According to Falvo et al., (2021), It was also be underlined that people could choose to continue participating or withdraw at any moment. Furthermore, the researcher protected the research participants from institutional vulnerability or category who were under the formal authority of others who might have different values, goals, and priorities than those of the potential research participant (Gordon, 2020). In this con-

text, the researcher devised a consent procedure that adequately insulated prospective subjects from the hierarchical system such that consent was secured from their school heads so that, their involvement did not compromise any significant events in the school. Moreover, the researcher acknowledged that certain participants may have been considered vulnerable due to factors such as age, gender, developmental stage, or specific circumstances (Lajoie et al., 2020). Likewise, the researcher discussed how the study incorporated appropriate ethical guidelines and safeguards to minimize potential risks. However, the researcher also acknowledged that not all participants may have been considered vulnerable, particularly in certain contexts. In such cases, the researcher explained that participants' involvement still held significance and contributed to the overall understanding of the realities of the education unit earners in teaching basic education science. Their perceptions offered insightful details on the different teaching experiences and issues employed within the occupation. Having both vulnerable and non-vulnerable participants, the study offered a more balanced and all-inclusive view of the education environment. The diversity of the opinions helped to gain a better understanding of the issues and approaches employed in the profession.

Risks, Benefits and Safety In terms of risk, benefits, and safety, the researcher obtained the participants' agreement and told them of the study's goal or purpose prior to its conduct. Participants were not forced to participate, and they were protected because there was a risk of being duped or threatened into taking part in the study. In addition, the IDI and FGD were conducted at the most convenient time for the participants to avoid hazards and assure their safety. Furthermore, the guide questions that were used in the IDI and FGD were evaluated by a panel of experts to ensure that the questions did not cause harm. The researcher conducted a thorough ex-

amination of potential risks and benefits, and a cautious approach was used both in obtaining consent and during the research procedure itself. In this study, participants were provided with both direct and indirect benefits as a result of their active involvement. Direct benefits included the giving of token and snacks after the interview as well as the access to new educational resources, and opportunities for self-reflection and personal growth. Indirect benefits encompassed the potential for their insights and experiences to contribute to improvements in educational practices, curriculum development, and policy reforms, benefiting the broader educational community. Additionally, participants had the opportunity for professional development, exposure to innovative instructional methods, and the chance to shape educational practices and policies. Their participation also fostered a sense of empowerment where their voices could help make a difference in meaningful change. This promoted greater participation throughout the research process and enhanced the validity of their contribution. Privacy and Confidentiality The researcher followed the values of transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the acquisition, keeping, and dispensation of personal information as outlined in the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researcher respected the participants' right to privacy. Unless otherwise compelled by law, the researcher must maintain the confidentiality of information at all times (Panel on Research Ethics, 2022). The researcher also ensured that the identities and personal information of the participants were kept strictly secret. The researcher specifically assured participants that their names and responses were kept secret. Furthermore, the researcher securely kept the surveys with significant data, transcriptions, photographs, and recordings that were recovered. Moreover, the data that were gathered in this study were safely kept in an electronic folder of the researcher's laptop that was password-protected to prevent

unauthorized access to the file but the researcher herself. After the research study was completed, the data collected were retained for three (3) years and be destroyed immediately thereafter in a secure manner that would prevent unauthorized access, use or disclosure to any other party or the public or in a manner prescribed by law (National Privacy Commission, 2022). Justice The researcher observed justice by selecting people for this qualitative phase of the research using proper sample techniques. This research was carried out with the utmost rigor and expertise, the participants were fairly selected, and the research was finished or carried out in the appropriate setting with enough facilities and expertise. Furthermore, the researcher treated all volunteers fairly, regardless of their status or position in the school. Aside from that, because the researcher utilized their time and effort, as well as disrupted their routines, they were given matching tokens of gratitude or any other type of reasonable and adequate incentive. Further, to ensure justice, participants' rights were protected, and the findings of this study were presented to the participants. Only those participants who possessed the inclusion criteria were qualified to be the research participant. However, there were no be any eligible volunteers that are turned away from this research due to gender, sex, socio-economic background, and ethnicity. In recognition of the potential inconvenience participants may have experienced while participating in the study, provisions were made to ensure equitable incentives. Participants were selected through a transparent and unbiased approach, considering diverse backgrounds, perspectives, and characteristics to ensure a representative sample. Special efforts were also made to avoid any potential biases or discrimination in the selection process. These provisions aimed to prioritize fairness, respect participants' contributions, and uphold ethical considerations throughout the study. Transparency Transparency was regarded as a crucial

component in this investigation. This helped participants understand that the major goal of the study was to unveil the realities of the education unit earners in teaching basic education science. Participants were also advised of any potential hazards or discomforts that may have arisen throughout the treatment. This aspect of ethical concern also included disclosing the research findings to the participants. As a result, the study's findings were adequately presented to the participants so that they understand the significance of the information that they had to contribute for the betterment of the various programs, projects, and activities down to their governance level. The researcher also ensured that the study's findings are correctly communicated in full breadth and correctness. To ensure widespread dissemination and accessibility of the study findings, measure were taken to facilitate the sharing of results. The findings were disseminated through various channels, such as academic conferences, peer-reviewed publications, and educational forums. Moreover, the researcher maintained clear and open communication with participants, providing them with detailed information about the study's procedures, purpose, and potential implications. They were encouraged to ask questions, seek clarifications, and provide feedback at various stages of the research.

Qualification of the Researcher

The researcher in control of the research study had to be morally strong, scientifically competent, socially aware, culturally sensitive, intellectually humble, observant, and equipped in safety matters. Based on her credentials, proficiency, and training, the researcher was more than capable of carrying out the research. In addition, the researcher was guided by her research adviser, who was more knowledgeable in research. The researcher decided to continue with this study because she believed she meets the criteria for executing the study competently, devising a meticulous design, and producing worthwhile predicted outcomes. This signified

that the researcher has the essential abilities and knowledge to carry out the specific study and was aware of the boundaries of personal competency in research.

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher ensured that the resources required for this study were readily available and easily accessible. For more readings and references, books, online journals, and unpublished dissertations were available, which gave a diverse literature and research that support the existence of the problem. Furthermore, the researcher was aware that audio recorders, and other equipment required for the study's execution were on hand. The researcher also sought consent from suitable institutions and offices. This indicates that with the availability of facilities and supplies, as well as effective communication, the researcher was able to perform and complete the study successfully. To ensure the adequacy of facilities for data gathering, the specific modality application to be used was identified. This included the use of the validated interview guide questions, computers, audio or video recording equipment, or online platforms. By identifying the specific modality application and utilizing appropriate resources, the study aimed to optimize data collection processes, ensure data accuracy, and enhance the overall quality of the research findings.

Community Involvement

Through a comprehensive dissemination plan, the study's findings were effectively communicated to participants, the school community they represented, and other stakeholders. Participants received detailed feedback and insights regarding their individual performance, allowing them to gain a deeper understanding of the realities of English teachers employing multimodal approach in literature class. To ensure broad dissemination of the benefits and results of this study, a well-defined dissemination plan was implemented. Communication channels such as school division offices, school learning action cells (LAC) sessions, training and seminar programs, and

other professional development initiatives were utilized to share the findings internally. This approach ensured that the participants and the broader school community were well-informed, raising awareness and promoting potential utilization of the study's outcomes. Moreover, the results of this study were communicated through public forums, providing an opportunity for wider sharing of the data. These forums enabled engagement with external stakeholders, fostering dialogue and facilitating the dissemination of valuable insights beyond the immediate educational community. The intention was to promote information sharing, generate awareness, and encourage potential application of the

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I was responsible for ensuring that the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I created an environment that encouraged open and honest exploration of ideas and promoted fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helped to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensured that the findings were reliable, and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I was familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possessed the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed and that the results were legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allowed me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gather information from various sources such as interviews

research findings in diverse educational contexts. Plagiarism and Fabrication Researchers strictly followed principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entailed giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors and maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

or observations, and I ensured accurate and secure storage of this information. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguard participants' privacy, and ensure that data was structured and available for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helped maintain the integrity of the research process and supported the production of credible, reliable findings that could be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives in accordance with the research query. I utilize meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were not only relevant but also contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I was tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through

written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensured that the research results are easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of findings, ensuring they were not only shared but

also understood and utilized by others in ways that could further knowledge and influence practice in the field. To achieve this, I utilized accessible language, and concise summaries targeted at the interests of educators, researchers, and policymakers.

2.7. Data Collection—In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. Several steps were taken in adherence to the proper data collection procedure. This was done in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing Endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal To initiate the data collection process, I secured endorsements from key stakeholders including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the last two weeks of October 2024, ensuring that all necessary permissions were in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proactive approach not only facilitated compliance with ethical standards but also fostered a cooperative environment among all parties involved.

Asking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This required submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and the process of participant identification. Moreover, I waited for the response from

the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was done in the first two weeks of November 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for Permission from the School Heads Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involved submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked for permission to conduct the study from the third week of November 2024 to the last week of the same month. Obtaining Consent from the Participants With the school heads' approval, I asked for consent from the research participants, through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explain the purpose of the research, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensured that the participants were fully informed and agreed to participate. Asking for consent from the participants was done in the last week of November 2024. Conducting the Interview Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. In-depth Interview (IDI) was utilized to gather the significant data from the participants following the purposive sampling. The interviews took place in the first two weeks of December 2024. Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' re-

marks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure used audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of partici-

2.8. Data Analysis—After collecting the data, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis. This involved methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allowed me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflected the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell’s Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants’ feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitated the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allowed researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. This process necessitates the identification

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I made use of Colaizzi’s method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences in employing multimodal approach in teaching literature. According to Co-

pants’ reactions. The transcription of interview responses was done on the third week of December 2024.

of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helped ensure that the analysis was both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study’s objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell’s Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there were multiple essential phases in Creswell’s Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes were examined and improved upon them to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme had a definition and name that elucidated the fundamental ideas. The last step entailed combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that clearly conveyed the study’s conclusions. This methodical approach guaranteed a comprehensive examination and enhanced the comprehension of the information.

Colaizzi’s (1978 as cited by Morrow et al., 2021) method featured a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminated in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which is validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relied on rich first-person accounts of experi-

ences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews were common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enabled researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intricate relationships between them (Craig et al., 2021). Experience among clinical instructors was investigated in another study using a seven-step process modified, verifying the method's flexibility and integrity in other educational environments (Healthcare, 2023). Transparency is ensured by the iterative process through independent coding and researcher agreement, enhancing trustworthiness (Sinfield et al., 2023). Educators' reflective practice has been investigated using the method in educational environments, verifying the application of the method outside of healthcare. Overall, the systematic, participant-verified seven-step process is a sound, systematic approach to phenomenological inquiry well into the post-2019 period.

Data Familiarization By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aimed to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process was crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. **Identifying Significant Statements** I will carefully identify every statement in the narratives that was directly related to the phenomenon I was studying. In order to identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—was conducted. This step was essential to ensure that my analysis stayed on topic and provided a strong basis for future thematic development.

Formulating Meanings After carefully examining the important statements, I determined meanings that are pertinent to the phenomenon.

Although Colaizzi admitted that complete bracketing was never truly possible, I had to reflexively "bracket" my own presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stayed rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entailed putting aside my own interpretations as was practical. **Clustering Themes** I ensured a rigorous analysis that remained true to the participants' experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes that are shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions had to be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, this preserves the integrity of the analysis. **Developing an Exhaustive Description** I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon that I wrote. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it was ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant had. **Producing the Fundamental Structure** I broke down the lengthy explanation into a succinct, concise statement that highlighted the key elements that I believed were crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. The essence of the participants' experiences was effectively and concisely communicated through this succinct synthesis, which concentrated on the essential components that were necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Deliberate analysis and careful consideration were required in the process in order not to miss any significant detail. Through this, I was able to preserve their depth and meaning of experiences while making the findings more understandable and meaningful.

Seeking Verification of the Fundamental

Structure I asked the participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflected their experience, either by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I went back and changed the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased, and the analysis was kept firmly based on the perspectives of the participants. The following figure illustrated this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data. This step served to further ensure that the interpretations did indeed relate to the participants lived realities, thus enhancing the validity of the research. Through the incorporation of their words, I was better able to refine the thematic framework

and ensure that it captured essentially the same meaning that they intended to convey. Participants enjoyed being involved in the process of validation because it ensured their voices were actually being heard. This added richness to the overall understanding of the phenomenon and improved the relationship between the findings and the lived experience. Involving participants in this way also facilitated a collaborative ethos that valued mutual respect and co-construction of knowledge. Lastly, it allowed me to identify and correct for any misinterpretation or bias that could have occurred during analysis. This two-way process provided another level of transparency to the research. Overall, this joined-up approach ensured the final outcomes were based on real, participant-driven insight.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study was about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results were, ensuring that the conclusions were trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study was. These considerations were further described below, according Ahmed (2024). Credibility Building credibility entailed proving that the results were accurate. Credibility was important for this study because it evaluated if the results accurately represented the realities and experiences of English teachers who employed a multimodal approach in teaching literature. I conversed with the participants for a long time in order to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also used triangulation, gathering information from a variety of sources, including observations, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. Transferability The degree to which the results of this study can be used in different situations or with different populations is re-

ferred to as transferability. While the particular insights were closely linked to teachers' experiences in a specific educational environment, I gave thorough explanations of the research context and methodology. Study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enabled other, educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well results applied to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability Confirmability deals with the study's objective by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I kept a thorough audit trail that detailed every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, in order to ensure confirmability. This methodological transparency made it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and going over the choices made. Dependability Dependability in this study was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods that were used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

that other researchers could duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results, such documentation validated the dependability of the research and. By following these standards, the research not only offered valid and trust-worthy conclusions regarding the effects of but it also provided a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the research questions underpinning the study are systematically presented alongside the answers derived from the responses of the participants. This analysis aims to illuminate the perspectives shared and deepen understanding of the subject at hand. This part of the study uncovers the lived experiences, strategies, and lessons learned from the English teachers in regarding multimodal approach in teaching literature. The emerging themes for the lived experiences of the English teachers are instructional transformation and learner responsiveness. Meanwhile, the strategies employed the English teachers include adaptive strategies, multisensory techniques, and inclusive practices. Thus, the themes for lessons learned are reflective growth and sustainable innovation.

3.1. Lived Experiences of the English Teachers Regarding Multimodal Approach in Teaching Literature—In exploring the complexities of literature instruction, the voices of English teachers reveal a rich tapestry of experiences and insights shaped by their engagement with multimodal approaches. These educators, standing at the intersection of traditional pedagogy and innovative teaching methods, navigate a landscape where visual, auditory, and textual elements converge to foster deeper literary understanding. Their lived experiences highlight how integrating diverse modalities enhances student engagement and transforms their teaching practices. As we delve into their narratives, we gain a nuanced appreciation of the challenges and triumphs they encounter, illuminating the profound impact these strategies can have on both educators and learners alike.

3.1.1. Instructional Transformation—English teachers are continually adapting their pedagogical practices to meet the evolving needs of their students. Embracing multimodal approaches in literature instruction allows educators to engage learners more deeply by integrating various visual, auditory, and textual elements. This shift in teaching methods reflects a dedication to fostering an inclusive learning environment where diverse perspectives can flourish. Through the narratives of the participants, we gain insights into how these transformations enhance teaching effectiveness and impact student learning experiences. The participants' narratives emphasize the imperative role of digital storytelling, graphic novels, and visual narratives, innovative tools that can enhance the literature curriculum through a multimodal approach. This is supported by the research conducted by Lin and Chang (2021), which highlights how integrating these multimodal texts fosters increased student interest and engagement. Incorporating visual elements in graphic novels aids students in grasping intricate themes and character development, making literary works more approachable. Engaging with these dynamic formats captivates students and promotes a deeper understanding of the material. Moreover, the multifaceted nature of the multimodal approach addresses the di-

verse learning styles present in any classroom. Bouchey et al. (2021) support this assertion, emphasizing the method's capability to accommodate varying learning preferences. They found that integrating visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements into literature instruction fosters inclusivity, enriching the educational experience for all learners. When students can interact with texts through multiple channels, they are more adept at comprehending and retaining information. This practice benefits traditional learners and supports those who excel in alternative learning environments, thereby making literature more accessible to everyone. These findings are further corroborated by Samat (2024), who examined the impact of multimedia presentations in literature classes. His research shows that students become more involved in their learning when creating presentations that blend text, images, and audio. This engagement heightens their understanding of themes and ideas and nurtures critical thinking and collaboration. Samat argues that when students take ownership of their learning through multimodal projects, their investment in literature deepens, enriching their overall educational experience. In addition, a study conducted by Rafiq et al. (2023) has demonstrated that incorporating digital tools and visual media into literature instruction significantly influences stu-

3.1.2. Learner Responsiveness—The journey of teaching literature offers English educators with valuable insights into how their instructional choices can align with the unique needs of their students. Teachers can create vibrant and inclusive learning environments by incorporating diverse methods that engage various modes of expression. This attentiveness to learners' diverse backgrounds and learning styles enhances classroom engagement and fosters a deeper appreciation for literature among all learners. Hence, embracing these dynamic interactions enables educators to effectively nur-

ture each learner's individuality, transforming their experiences with literature into more meaningful and enriching encounters. As we delve into the second theme, the following statements from participants highlight the significance of tailoring literature instruction to meet the diverse needs of learners. The study of CALM International Mental Health and Wellness Services (2023) aligned with the narratives of the English teachers. It highlights the significance of incorporating multimodal resources in literature classes to address the diverse needs of learners. Exposing learners to various cultural

dent engagement and learning outcomes. The authors found that students who engaged with multimodal texts, such as video adaptations and interactive e-books, exhibited enhanced understanding and critical thinking skills. This approach allows educators to reach visual learners who thrive on imagery and graphics and auditory learners who benefit from narrative discussions. The study underscores the importance of flexibility in teaching methods, suggesting that such adaptability creates a more personalized learning experience that ultimately leads to improved academic performance. The first theme emphasizes the transformative power of digital storytelling, graphic novels, and visual narratives in reshaping literature instruction through a multimodal approach. By integrating visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements, this method redefines traditional teaching, making complex literary themes more accessible and engaging. It caters to diverse learning styles, fostering an inclusive environment where every student can actively connect with the material. Creating multimodal projects deepens understanding and promotes critical thinking, collaboration, and student agency. Thus, educators can incorporate digital tools and interactive media to create a personalized and flexible learning experience that transforms students' engagement and academic success in literature.

ture each learner's individuality, transforming their experiences with literature into more meaningful and enriching encounters. As we delve into the second theme, the following statements from participants highlight the significance of tailoring literature instruction to meet the diverse needs of learners. The study of CALM International Mental Health and Wellness Services (2023) aligned with the narratives of the English teachers. It highlights the significance of incorporating multimodal resources in literature classes to address the diverse needs of learners. Exposing learners to various cultural

perspectives through mediums such as films, music, and digital storytelling enhances their engagement and appreciation for literary texts. This approach respects the rich backgrounds of learners and allows them to create personal connections with the material, fostering a more responsive learning environment. In the same vein, research indicates that learners who interact with texts through multiple visual, auditory, and kinesthetic formats are more inclined to succeed. Kress (2020) emphasizes that integrating digital storytelling into literature classes increases motivation and engagement, allowing learners to create narratives using various media. This collaborative effort allows learners to express their understanding uniquely, catering to their individual preferences and learning needs. Samat (2024) further supports this perspective by highlighting the positive impact of multimedia presentations on learner involvement in literature classes. When learners create presentations that blend text, images, and audio, their active participation in the learning process deepens. It enhances their grasp of literary themes and nurtures critical thinking and collaboration skills. Learners become more invested in their education by taking ownership of their learning through multimodal projects, resulting in a richer and more responsive educational experience. Moreover, the ability to cater to diverse learning styles enhances the overall educational experience for all learners. Bouchey et al. (2021) recognize this crucial aspect, noting that integrating various modes of communication promotes inclusivity in literature classes. Their findings reveal that learners

engaged with texts through multiple channels exhibit improved comprehension and retention. This approach effectively supports traditional learners while accommodating those who thrive in alternative learning environments, making literature more accessible and responsive to a broader audience. Additionally, Linder and Ross (2024) discussed that multimodal pedagogy invites learners to synthesize information from diverse sources, fostering a deeper understanding and critical engagement with the material. By analyzing videos, infographics, and traditional texts, learners are encouraged to identify underlying messages and biases, resulting in a more nuanced interpretation of content. The study further validates this approach, demonstrating that multimodal resources enhance critical reflection and expression, enriching the educational landscape and responding adeptly to learner needs. The findings highlight the significance of integrating multimodal resources in literature instruction to enhance learner responsiveness. This approach fosters deeper engagement and personal connections with the material by exposing students to various mediums. It allows students to connect their unique backgrounds and learning preferences to the content, creating a more inclusive and responsive learning environment. Engaging with different formats supports diverse learning styles. Moreover, it improves comprehension and retention while encouraging active participation. This method deepens students' understanding of literary themes and cultivates critical thinking and collaboration- ensuring learners are more actively involved in their educational experience.

3.2. Strategies English Teachers Used to Implement a Multimodal Approach in Teaching Literature—Integrating innovative teaching methods in literature instruction has become essential as education evolves, particularly through a multimodal approach. The sec-

ond research question focuses on the English teachers' effective strategies to engage students in literature through interactive storytelling, digital media, group performances, and creative projects. Examining how these diverse pedagogical methods enhance student engagement

Fig. 3. Lived Experiences of English Teachers Regarding the Multimodal Approach in Teaching Literature

and comprehension aims to uncover best practices that foster a more inclusive and dynamic literary education- enriching the experience and

accommodating the varied learning styles in today's classrooms.

3.2.1. Adaptive Strategies—Exploring human behavior in response to changing circumstances highlights the importance of adaptive strategies. When faced with challenges, individuals and groups often exhibit remarkable resilience and creativity, employing various tactics to navigate uncertainty. These strategies can range from altering daily routines to applying innovative problem-solving techniques, reflecting the dynamic nature of human adaptation. Insights from educators further illuminate this theme, showcasing the diverse multimodal strategies they use in teaching literature, which help them effectively manage change and uncertainty in the classroom. This is reinforced by the study of Noroozi et al. (2020), which highlights that English teachers who effectively implement multimodal approaches often utilize adaptive strategies to cater to diverse student needs. By providing an array of tools and resources, such as basic tutorials and links to online platforms, teachers empower students to navigate new technologies independently without needing to become experts in every medium. This strategy alleviates pressure on educators while fostering student autonomy. According to Aguiar (2019), multimodal assignments, which allow students to create projects using various media formats like videos, podcasts, and digital presentations, foster the exploration of diverse expressive avenues. These assignments address different learning styles and resonate with the digital landscape that students are familiar with. Educators have observed that when students are free to choose their preferred means of communication—whether traditional essays or more innovative formats such as memes, visual journals, or podcasts. Through this, they exhibit increased engagement and produce higher-quality work.

This trend underscores the importance of flexibility in assignment design, aligning educational practices with the interests and skills of modern learners. The narratives also demonstrate that teachers adapt their multimodal activities to effectively address specific learning needs, leveraging technology to enhance engagement and resourcefulness. As mentioned in the study of Suwastini et al. (2021), English teachers are increasingly inclined to embrace interactive and student-centred pedagogies that weave linguistic and visual elements together. Tailoring activities to align with students' interests and requirements enables educators to navigate challenges and foster deeper engagement and comprehension. Pan and Zhang's (2021) research also emphasize that Chinese high school teachers employed various multimodal practices. These include animations, videos, and colour-coded texts to stimulate students' interest in reading English literature. Teachers could promote greater involvement and curiosity by eliciting students' multisensory responses. The study advocates for incorporating more multimodal resources to address the diverse learning needs in the classroom, ultimately improving literacy outcomes. Furthermore, as highlighted by Hidayat et al. (2024), teachers recognize that integrating multimodal texts through a Genre-Based Approach enhances students' critical thinking and accommodates various learning styles. This realization underscores the importance of thoughtful planning and preparation, which can help overcome initial hurdles related to technical skills and resource accessibility. Likewise, Walsh (2019) argues that multimodal literacy practices make students capable of reading and meaning-making with and through different communicative modes. His

findings suggest that such practices, in addition to making students perform academically, also make them perform learner autonomy and digital literacy. Overall, the findings illustrate how

3.2.2. *Multisensory Techniques*—English teachers increasingly utilize multisensory techniques as part of a multimodal approach to literature instruction, acknowledging that engaging various learning styles enhances students' comprehension and enjoyment. Through strategies such as incorporating visual aids, auditory elements, and hands-on activities, educators create immersive experiences that deepen students' connections to the texts. Many educators highlight the effectiveness of this approach, noting that learners thrive in an environment where they can interact with literature through various senses. More so, engaging multiple modalities opens new pathways to understanding. Using multisensory techniques in teaching literature can significantly enhance the educational experience for students. Educators can use a multimodal approach to create a vibrant and engaging learning environment that allows students to connect more deeply with literary works. Similarly, Kleftodimos (2024) emphasized the importance of incorporating animations and interactive activities that enable students to immerse themselves in narratives through sensory channels. It enriches their emotional understanding of the texts and supports the development of their emotional literacy. When students experience literature in this dynamic manner, they tend to grasp complex themes and concepts, enhancing both the depth of their interpretations and the quality of classroom discussions. Additionally, Heilporn et al. (2021) underscore the significance of the multisensory approach. For example, replacing traditional written quizzes with creative video responses can encourage students to engage more thoroughly with the content, allowing them to develop their oral and visual communication skills. These incre-

adaptive strategies in implementing multimodal approaches can significantly amplify student engagement and creativity in literature.

mental changes build students' confidence in utilizing various modes of expression while upholding academic rigour. On the other hand, Palioura and Dimoulas (2022) also highlight the role of digital storytelling as another powerful tool in a multisensory approach. Educators can facilitate a deeper understanding of literary themes and techniques by allowing students to create and analyze narratives using multimedia elements. This method effectively fosters exploration and engagement with the material, enriching the overall learning experience in literature classes. Moreover, Esplendori et al., (2022) indicate that integrating multisensory methods improves teaching effectiveness and optimizes the use of educational resources. Presenting complex information through diverse modalities enables teachers to enhance overall teaching quality and support better student outcomes. Furthermore, data mining technologies can streamline access to a wealth of resources, aiding educators in creating more effective lesson plans. Lastly, interactive techniques that stimulate participation through visual and auditory means can significantly enhance student engagement in literature classes. As stipulated in the study of Joy (2024), utilizing a variety of multimodal resources, teachers can elevate student involvement and comprehension, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and interactive classroom atmosphere. Overall, multisensory techniques in literature teaching create a more engaging and inclusive learning environment by allowing students to explore texts through visual, auditory, and interactive methods. These approaches deepen emotional understanding, enhance expression, and support better comprehension, making literature more accessible and meaningful.

3.2.3. Inclusive Practices—In diverse classrooms where students come with varying abilities, backgrounds, and learning preferences, English teachers often face the challenge of making literature accessible and engaging for all. The multimodal approach integrates different modes and offers a flexible path toward inclusivity. Teachers adapt this approach to enrich the learning experience and ensure that every student finds a point of connection with the text. As they navigate the complexities of classroom diversity, English teachers develop thoughtful strategies that allow all learners to participate meaningfully in literary discussions and interpretations. The statements are supported by the study of Naji et al. (2019), which emphasizes that integrating digital platforms into literature education enhances cultural literacy by linking classical works with modern media. Such interactive projects enable students to explore how ancient texts can be retold or reinterpreted in digital formats, effectively bridging the gap between traditional literature and contemporary digital culture. This approach deepens students' understanding of these texts and nurtures creativity and innovation in literary analysis. Furthermore, integrating multimodal literacy strategies empowers teachers to foster increased student engagement and improve communication skills. Sutrisno et al. (2023) highlight that student feedback is crucial for revising these multimodal strategies, ultimately leading to more effective learning experiences that cater to diverse learning needs. In addition, Von Gillern (2022) underscores that when teachers adopt multimodal approaches to literature, the aes-

thetic dimensions of these texts significantly enhance student creativity and engagement. Teachers have discovered the importance of incorporating various forms of media, such as films and games, alongside traditional texts to better resonate with students' interests. This approach promotes student autonomy, allowing learners to explore literary texts creatively. Recognizing the value of these diverse media, teachers can create a more inclusive classroom environment that meets different learning preferences. Moreover, the narrative literature review findings reveal that teachers effectively address the challenges of multimodal teaching by tailoring activities to meet specific learning needs. Educators create more inclusive practices by utilizing technology to overcome resource limitations and boost student interest. Suwastini et al. (2021) advocate for increased focus on teacher training and development to support the implementation of multimodal instructional approaches. This professional development is essential for equipping teachers with the skills necessary to embrace inclusive strategies that cater to their students' varied strengths. Ultimately, integrating digital platforms and multimodal strategies in literature education plays a pivotal role in fostering inclusive practices in the classroom. Combining traditional texts with various media forms fosters educators to engage students better and accommodate diverse learning preferences. Thus, it empowers them to explore and interpret literary works creatively. This approach enhances student autonomy and allows for tailored activities that address specific learning needs.

3.3. Lessons Learned from Implementing Multimodal Approach in Teaching Literature — The multimodal approach to teaching English offers a way to make literature more engaging and meaningful for learners. Through this

method, teachers aim to connect with learners more effectively by using varied forms of communication. Their experiences provide important insights into how this approach supports learning and addresses classroom challenges.

3.3.1. Reflective Growth—

Fig. 4. Strategies English Teachers Used to Implement a Multimodal Approach in Teaching Literature

Implementing a multimodal approach to teaching literature has transformed the learning experience, pushing educators and students to move beyond traditional methods. The process involved navigating challenges, balancing diverse learning styles with technology, and discovering new ways to engage students. This shift emphasized adaptability, creativity, and inclusivity, fostering deeper connections to the material. The reflections from participants highlight the personal and professional insights gained, with resilience and innovation emerging as key aspects of their growth. Teachers have reported significant practice growth by incorporating innovative multimodal approaches to enhance students’ oral English proficiency and motivation. As Lee et al. (2023) noted, this reflective growth “illustrates how multimodal literacy strategies empower educators to foster greater student engagement and communication skills, emphasizing the importance of merging visual, auditory, and digital elements to create

impactful learning experiences.” Additionally, Sutrisno et al. (2024) emphasize that the study of multimodal learning strategies highlights the importance of engaging students through various channels of communication and expression. Educators can create more dynamic and inclusive learning environments by incorporating visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements into lessons. This approach caters to different learning styles and fosters greater student engagement and retention of material, ultimately leading to more effective educational outcomes. Noroozi et al. (2020) also emphasize the journey of reflective growth among educators who effectively implement multimodal tasks by providing students with a diverse range of tools and resources. By offering basic tutorials and directing students to online platforms, teachers foster student independence and reduce the pressure of mastering every technology themselves. This progressive shift enables educators to focus on nurturing creativity and thought

processes, employing flexible grading rubrics prioritizing content over specific media conventions. Such changes demonstrate a commitment to cultivating student motivation and creativity, creating a more inclusive and dynamic learning environment. Meanwhile, Duan (2021) reinforces the findings. According to his study, it showcases the impact of platforms like Inanimate Alice and other digital storytelling tools in the classroom, highlighting the transformative experience for teachers. These resources empower students to engage with narratives across various media, deepening their interaction with the content. Students use choice-based progression and multimedia elements to immerse themselves in a more interactive learning atmosphere. This pedagogical shift enhances their engagement with literary content. It fosters critical thinking and narrative-building skills, illustrating teachers' adaptability in meeting the growing demand for innovative and student-centred learning environments. Finally, Laadem and Mallahi (2020) emphasize how teachers who hate teachers embrace multimodal pedagogies that prioritize interactive and student-centred

approaches, effectively blending linguistic and visual elements in their teaching. They have tailored their activities to address students' interests and needs, overcoming challenges that enhance engagement and understanding. This reflective study highlights the crucial importance of rethinking students' strategies to align with multimodal requirements, underscoring the significant professional growth of teachers in this continually evolving educational landscape. Incorporating multimodal approaches in education has significantly improved students' oral English proficiency and motivation. By merging various forms of communication, teachers have created dynamic and inclusive learning environments that cater to diverse learning styles. This innovative method engages students more effectively and fosters critical thinking and creativity, allowing educators to focus on nurturing these skills in a more interactive atmosphere. Ultimately, the shift toward multimodal literacy strategies demonstrates a commitment to enhancing educational outcomes while adapting to the evolving needs of learners.

3.3.2. Sustainable Innovation—In today's educational landscape, there is an intense desire and advocacy for long-term, contextual, and culturally rooted multimodal practices. Effective teachers understand that engagement transcends traditional methods, incorporating diverse media and formats that resonate with students' unique backgrounds and experiences. By creating a dynamic learning environment that prioritizes cultural relevance, educators enhance learner understanding and prepare them to navigate the complexities of the modern world. This approach reinforces promoting a comprehensive view of literacy, ensuring that students are equipped to thrive in a diverse and interconnected society while actively contributing to their communities. Teachers are decisively

adopting innovative and sustainable practices by implementing interactive and student-centered approaches seamlessly blending linguistic and visual elements. Comparable to the study of Laadem and Mallahi (2020), it emphasizes the imperative role of tailoring activities to their students' interests and educators to significantly boost engagement and understanding, demonstrating a strong commitment to evolving pedagogical strategies that meet multimodal needs. In the same spectrum, study by Nguyen Pardede (2024) highlights the relevance of sustainable innovation in a multimodal approach by prioritizing collaborative discussions and learner-centered methods. As they receive targeted training and support, their confidence in utilizing multimodal learning opportunities increases,

underscoring critical role of mentorship and professional development in effectively integrating new teaching techniques. The study of Sibanda (2024) highlights the essential nature of resource-sharing and peer support as vital components of sustainable education. Teachers effectively overcome resource shortages through strategic collaboration with colleagues and the pursuit of alternative teaching aids. Their innovative methodologies emphasize critical and analytical thinking, successfully engaging students with poetry and literature. Furthermore, Kim and Kang (2020) highlight how collaborative multimodal composing fosters sustainable innovation in education by encouraging creative and meaningful engagement with content. Integrating tools like Adobe Spark to combine text, images, and sound in literature classrooms allows students to explore literary themes through diverse modes of expression. This deepens their understanding and promotes innovative thinking and long-term engagement with literary study, supporting a more sustainable and inclusive approach to teaching literature. Lastly, Pan and Zhang (2020) also found a positive impact of

teachers significantly influencing learning by using multimodal practices such as animations, videos, and color-coded texts to captivate students' interest in reading English. Their focus on fostering multisensory engagement drives increased student involvement. The findings advocate for integrating even more multimodal tools to meet diverse learning needs while enhancing literacy outcomes, firmly establishing sustainable innovation as a cornerstone of modern education. In conclusion, sustainable innovation in teaching literature through a multimodal approach center on creative, long-term practices that respond to the varied needs of learners. The insights shared by teachers underscore the value of multimodal strategies in deepening student engagement and making literary learning more meaningful. These practices enhance comprehension and nurture enduring interest in literature, particularly when they reflect cultural relevance and utilize accessible resources. Ultimately, this approach supports ongoing reflection, adaptability, and inclusive teaching, even in contexts with limited

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of the study's findings and discusses their implications for future research directions. The primary objective of this research was to examine the lived experiences, strategies, and lessons learned in implementing multimodal approach in teaching literature among English teachers.

4.1. Findings—To achieve the research objectives, I utilized a qualitative phenomenological approach combined with thematic analysis. Following the guidelines set by Creswell (2018), I employed open-ended questions during interviews to gain an authentic understanding of participants' experiences. This interview method encouraged participants to discuss openly and fully their definitions and meanings related to the phenomenon being studied, specifically the narratives of English teachers in im-

plementing multimodal approach. According to the study's findings, the thematic analysis revealed the emerging themes: transformative instruction and learner responsiveness for the lived experiences of English teachers in implementing multimodal approach in teaching literature; adaptive strategies, multimodal techniques, and inclusive practices for the strategies used to implement multimodal approach in teaching literature; lastly, reflective growth and sustainable innovation for the lessons learned in imple-

Fig. 5. Lessons Learned from Implementing Multimodal Approach In Teaching Literature.

menting multimodal approach in teaching literature. In response to the first research question, which sought to describe the lived experiences of English teachers in implementing the multimodal approach, the participants revealed how this method brought about transformative instruction. Teachers expressed how multimodal strategies encouraged them to shift from conventional, text-based instruction to more interactive and engaging methods. Incorporating multiple modes such as visuals, audio materials, dramatizations, and digital media transformed their teaching practices and renewed their enthusiasm for delivering literature lessons. The change was not limited to techniques alone; it also reshaped their mindset about engaging students in literary learning. Closely tied to this transformation was the emergence of learner responsiveness. Teachers noticed students became more attentive, participative, and motivated when exposed to multimodal instruction. This responsiveness manifested in increased curiosity, deeper engagement with texts, and improved communication of literary understanding. As students began to connect more personally with the materials, teachers were more inspired to create lessons that resonated with their learners' interests and learning styles. The observed responsiveness of learners validated the teachers' efforts and reinforced their commitment to sustaining a multimodal approach. The second research question focused on teachers' strategies to implement the multimodal approach in teaching literature. The theme of adaptive strategies emerged as teachers described how they continuously adjusted their teaching to align with their students' learning needs. They employed flexible lesson designs, modified activities on the spot, and responded to classroom dynamics with creativity and sensitivity. This adaptability was essential in managing varying classroom contexts and ensuring that instruction remained effective and inclusive. Additionally, the theme of multimodal techniques de-

scribed the specific instructional methods used by teachers. Participants mentioned using resources such as short films, podcasts, graphic organizers, role-playing, and visual presentations to help students explore and appreciate literary texts. These techniques made abstract literary concepts more tangible and supported learners in constructing deeper meaning. The variety of tools and media helped bridge gaps in understanding and sustained student interest throughout the lesson. Also central to the discussion was the theme of inclusive practices. Teachers intentionally incorporated materials and activities that reflected diverse backgrounds and learning profiles. It included integrating culturally relevant literature, providing differentiated outputs, and allowing students to express their understanding through various modes such as art, music, or movement. Teachers shared that multimodal instruction allowed them to reach learners who might otherwise struggle in a traditional, text-heavy environment. Creating an inclusive learning atmosphere nurtured a sense of belonging and participation among all students. The third research question explored the lessons English teachers learned using the multimodal approach. One key insight was reflective growth. Teachers recognized the value of self-evaluation in refining their teaching practices. They often revisited their strategies, noted student responses, and adjusted future lessons accordingly. This continuous cycle of reflection helped them become more intentional in their instructional choices and deepened their understanding of how students learn literature through multiple modes. Finally, the theme of sustainable innovation captured the teachers' hopes for long-term support in implementing multimodal practices. While they demonstrated dedication and initiative, teachers strongly needed institutional backing through resources, training, and collaborative planning time. They envisioned a future where the multimodal approach could be integrated into school

policies and curriculum frameworks to ensure its long-term impact. With appropriate support, teachers believed that the benefits of multimodal instruction, such as improved student engagement and inclusive learning, could be sustained and expanded. Overall, the findings reveal that the multimodal approach is not only a method of

instruction but a catalyst for growth and transformation among English teachers. Their experiences underscore the importance of responsiveness, adaptability, and reflection in delivering literature instruction that is engaging, inclusive, and meaningful.

4.2. Implications—The findings of this study yield several important implications for teaching practice, curriculum development, teacher training, and policy formulation, particularly concerning the implementation of the multimodal approach in teaching literature. The themes that emerged from the teachers' lived experiences highlight the transformative potential of multimodal instruction and the need for systemic support to sustain its benefits. From a pedagogical standpoint, the findings imply that the multimodal approach fosters deeper engagement and understanding among learners by allowing them to construct meaning through various modes of representation. Aligned with Constructivism Theory, which emphasizes active knowledge construction through experience and interaction, multimodal techniques enable learners to connect literature with their prior knowledge, cultural backgrounds, and real-life contexts. Teachers observed that learners became more responsive and participative. It further suggests that they tend to engage critically and creatively with texts when instruction is diversified and learner-centered. Moreover, the findings underscore the relevance of the Multiliteracies Theory, which advocates for including multiple forms of literacy in today's increasingly diverse and digitally mediated learning environments. Teachers responded to learners' varied cultural and linguistic backgrounds through adaptive strategies and inclusive practices by incorporating diverse media and modes. This

highlights the need to redefine what it means to be literate in the digital age and to ensure that literature instruction embraces visual, auditory, spatial, and gestural literacies alongside traditional print. Regarding professional practice, reflective growth, and sustainable innovation themes suggest that teacher development programs emphasize ongoing reflection and encourage experimentation with multimodal resources. Reflective teaching practices help educators adapt to learners' evolving needs, while sustained innovation requires access to training, time, and collaboration. Therefore, schools and institutions are encouraged to provide professional development opportunities rooted in theoretical foundations and practical application of multimodal strategies. In addition, curriculum developers and school leaders are encouraged to integrate multimodal principles into literature curricula. Lessons should be designed to accommodate multiple learning modes, allowing learners to demonstrate understanding in diverse ways. The findings support the need to move beyond rigid textual analysis and promote more interactive, inclusive, and culturally responsive learning experiences. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that a multimodal approach can enhance literature instruction, making it more meaningful, inclusive, and centered on the learner. However, systemic support is crucial to fully unlock its potential, empowering teachers and fostering innovation in classroom practices.

4.3. Future Directions—

Based on the study's findings, the insights gained must be communicated and meaningfully applied by the key stakeholders for whom this research is intended. **Learners** Implementing multimodal instruction directly benefits learners, showing how various modes of representation can make literature more accessible and engaging. Students are more likely to develop critical thinking and creativity when interacting with texts through multiple forms, such as videos, infographics, and digital media. **The research demonstrates that multimodal approaches promote more profound understanding and active participation, empowering students to connect with literature in meaningful ways that resonate with their experiences and backgrounds.** **Teachers** This study provides practical insights among English teachers into the benefits and challenges of implementing multimodal instruction in the classroom. Various modes can enhance student engagement, critical thinking, and learning outcomes. The findings can be applied to refine teaching methods, experiment with new multimodal techniques, and better meet students' diverse needs, ultimately improving the ability to create inclusive, student-centered learning environments. **School Heads** Findings can be utilized to foster a culture that embraces innovation and inclusivity in literature instruction. The research emphasizes the importance of adapting to diverse learning styles and backgrounds, helping prioritize multimodal strategies in curriculum planning. Insights from the study inform decision-making processes related to resource allocation, staff training, and initiatives that support teachers and students in adopting and sustaining multimodal practices. **Educational Leaders** This study provides valuable insights among educational leaders into

how multimodal instruction can transform literature teaching and learning. Understanding the impact of diverse teaching strategies allows for advocacy and facilitation of multimodal approaches in schools. The research serves as a guide for supporting professional development programs, allocating resources for multimodal tools, and creating policies that promote innovative teaching methods, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes across diverse student populations. **Other Stakeholders** The study also informs other stakeholders by illustrating the positive impact of multimodal teaching on student outcomes. Emphasizing the importance of collaboration to support innovative instructional practices, the findings can be utilized to advocate for policies promoting equitable access to resources, support for teacher training, and ensuring schools are equipped with the necessary tools for implementing multimodal strategies that benefit all students. **Future Researchers** For future researchers, this study lays a foundation for further exploration into the effectiveness and sustainability of multimodal instruction in various educational settings. Findings encourage deeper investigations into how multimodal techniques influence student learning across diverse disciplines and age groups. This work can be expanded by examining the long-term impact of multimodal approaches, the role of technology in teaching, and the potential for applying multimodal strategies beyond literature instruction to other subjects. Comparative research across various cultural and regional settings could provide insights on how multimodal pedagogy is used across the world. Future studies could also consider taking into account the views of students themselves on their attitudes, issues, and perceptions about multimodal learning.

5. References

- Afzal, A., Khan, S., Daud, S., Ahmad, Z., & Butt, A. (2023). Addressing the digital divide: Access and use of technology in education. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(2), 883–895. <https://doi.org/10.54183/jssr.v3i2.326>
- Aguiar, C. (2019). Going multimodal, tips for making the switch to multimodal assignments.
- Ahmed, S. K. (2024). The pillars of trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health*, 2, Article 100051. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glmedi.2024.100051>
- Alqahtani, M. (2021). The impact of multimodal learning on literacy outcomes: A review of the literature. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19388071.2020.1822580>
- Anis, M. (2023). Integrating multimodal approach in english language teaching.
- Asmawi, A., & Alam, M. S. (2024). Qualitative research: Understanding its underlying philosophies. *Forum for Education Studies*, 2(2), Article 1320. <https://doi.org/10.59400/fes.v2i2.1320>
- Aspers, P. (2009). Empirical phenomenology: A qualitative research approach (the cologne seminars). *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3606033>
- Aspers, P., & Corte, U. (2019). What is qualitative in qualitative research. *Qualitative Sociology*, 42(2), 139–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-019-9413-7>
- Barcelona, A. B., & Dela Cruz, S. B. (2024). Empowering online learners: The role of volitional competence, grit and metacognitive awareness in online learning. *Journal of Educators Online*, 21(3), n.p. <https://doi.org/10.9743/JEO.2024.21.3.2>
- Bhappu, A. D., Blomqvist, K., Andreeva, T., Zappa, P., Yeo, M. L., & Lempiälä, T. (2020). Providers' initial trust on an organization-sponsored sharing platform: The framing of coworker collaborative consumption. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 2174. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02174>
- Bouchev, B., Castek, J., & Thygeson, J. (2021). Multimodal learning. In *Handbook of research on digital learning*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58948-6_3
- Caramay, M., Maningas, R., Yazon, A., Manaig, K., & Tesoro, J. (2023). Lived experiences of english literature teachers in a digitalized classroom: A phenomenological study. *Journal of English as A Foreign Language Teaching and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.31098/jefltr.v3i2.1695>
- Caulfield, J. (2019). How to do thematic analysis.
- Chand, S. P. (2024). Constructivism in education: Exploring the contributions of piaget, vygotsky, and bruner. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 12(7), 274–278. <https://doi.org/10.21275/SR23630021800>
- Clinical instructors' perspectives on the assessment of clinical knowledge of undergraduate nursing students: A descriptive phenomenological approach. (2023). *Healthcare*, 11(13), 1851. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11131851>
- Craig, S. L., McInroy, L. B., Goulden, A., & Eaton, A. D. (2021). Engaging the senses in qualitative research via multimodal coding: Triangulating transcript, audio, and video data in a study with sexual and gender minority youth. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20(4), Article 16094069211013659. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211013659>

- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th). SAGE Publications.
- Crotty, M. (2020). *The foundations of social research*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115700>
- Dawadi, S. (2020). Thematic analysis approach: A step by step guide for elt research practitioners. *Journal of NELTA*, 25(1–2), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.3126/nelta.v25i1-2.49731>
- De Abreu, B. (2021). *Skills for life: Media literacy and critical thinking*. Inter-American Development Bank. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0003779>
- De Lima Guedes, K. K., & Mar-Molinero, V. (2021). The challenges of dynamic teacher training for a short english for academic purposes course when using multimodal digital platforms: A case study. In N. Zoghalmi, C. Brudermann, C. Sarré, M. Grosbois, L. Bradley, & S. Thouësny (Eds.), *Call and professionalisation: Short papers from eurocall 2021* (pp. 69–74). Research-publishing.net. <https://doi.org/10.14705/rpnet.2021.54.1311>
- DeHart, J. (2023, May). *Guiding students to develop multimodal literacy* [Accessed: 2025-06-16]. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/guiding-students-develop-multimodal-literacy>
- Djamdjuri, D. S., Gatot, M., Yusiyaka, R. A., Sahril, M., Mufaridah, F., & Pratama, M. I. (2023). Systematic literature review: Integrating islamic education in english language teaching. *Journal of English Education and Teaching*, 7(4), 881–900. <https://doi.org/10.33369/jeet.7.4.881-900>
- Drewry, R. J., Cumming Potvin, W. M., & Maor, D. (2019). New approaches to literacy problems: Multiliteracies and inclusive pedagogies. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 44(11), 61–78. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1243232>
- Duan, Y. (2021). Multimodal and multidimensional interactive teaching mode of comprehensive english under the background of big data. In *Proceedings of the 2021 international conference on artificial intelligence and education (icaied)*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62743-0_89
- Esplendori, G. F., Kobayashi, R. M., & Püschel, V. A. A. (2022). Multisensory integration approach, cognitive domains, meaningful learning: Reflections for undergraduate nursing education. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP*, 56, e20210381. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-220X-REEUSP-2021-0381>
- Falvo, I., Fiordelli, M., Amati, R., Ibnidris, A., Albanese, E., & Fadda, M. (2021). Participants' comprehension of the informed consent in an epidemiological study on dementia prevalence: A qualitative study. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 12, Article 656822. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.656822>
- Farías, M., & Véliz, L. (2019). Multimodal texts in chilean english teaching education: Experiences from educators and pre-service teachers. *PROFILE Issues in Teachers' Professional Development*, 21(2), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.15446/profile.v21n2.75172>
- Gautam, V. K., & Gautam, J. (2023). Qualitative research approaches in social sciences (version 1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10428694>
- Gonçalves, C., & Dias, D. (2023). Engaging students through social media in literature classes: A multimodal approach [Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Daniel-Goncalves-21>]. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Daniel-Goncalves-21>
- Gordon, B. G. (2020). Vulnerability in research: Basic ethical concepts and general approach to review. *Ochsner Journal*, 20(1), 34–38. <https://doi.org/10.31486/toj.19.0079>

- Guan, Y. (2023). Characteristics of teaching english and american literature based on multimodality under language acquisition theory. *Applied Mathematics and Nonlinear Sciences*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.2478/amns.2023.2.00978>
- Health, C. I. M., & Services, W. (2023). Understanding and supporting the diverse learning styles of children.
- Heilporn, G., Lakhal, S., & Bélisle, M. (2021). An examination of teachers' strategies to foster student engagement in blended learning in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00260-3>
- Hennink, M., & Kaiser, B. N. (2022). Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests. *Social Science Medicine*, 292, 114523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114523>
- Hidayat, M. R. Y., Defitri, S. Y., & Hilman, H. (2024). The impact of artificial intelligence (ai) on financial management [DOI not yet assigned; placeholder used]. *Productivity*, 10(4), Article 35. <https://doi.org/10.XXXX/ppipbr.prod.v10i4.35>
- Hong, A. L., & Tan, K. H. (2020). A review of theories and practices of multiliteracies in classroom: Issues and trends. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(11), 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.11.3>
- Hwang, S., & Foote, J. D. (2021). Why do people participate in small online communities? *Proceedings of the ACM on Human–Computer Interaction*, 5(CSCW2), Article 462. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3479606>
- Jiang, L., Yu, S., & Zhao, Y. (2020). An efl teacher's investment in digital multimodal composing. *ELT Journal*, 74, 297–306. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccaa010>
- Joshi, B. M., Khatiwada, S. P., & Pokhrel, R. K. (2024). Influence of socioeconomic factors on access to digital resources for education. *Rupantaran: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 8(1), 17–33. <https://doi.org/10.3126/rupantaran.v8i01.65197>
- Joy, M. L. (2024, November). Studies and literature on multimodal reading in the philippines: A literature review. <https://www.studocu.com/ph/document/naguilian-national-high-school/science-technology-engineering-and-mathematics/studies-and-literature-on-multimodal-reading-in-the-philippines/120197649>
- Karatza, S. (2022). The “multimodal literacy in the efl classroom” workshop as a design for learning. *Designs for Learning*, 14(1), 112–128. <https://doi.org/10.16993/dfl.188>
- Kim, Y., & Kang, S. (2020). Writing to make meaning through collaborative multimodal composing among korean efl learners: Writing processes, writing quality and student perception. *Computers and Composition*, 58–59, 102609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compcom.2020.102609>
- Kleftodimos, A. (2024). Computer animated videos in education: A comprehensive review and teacher experiences from animation creation. *Digital*, 4(3), 613–647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/digital4030031>
- Kress, G. (2020). *Literacy in the new media age*. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/Literacy-in-the-New-Media-Age/Kress/p/book/9780415290746>
- Kummin, S., Surat, S., Kuty, F. M., Othman, Z., & Muslim, N. (2020). The use of multimodal texts in teaching english language oral skills. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(12), 7015–7021. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.081269>

- Laadem, M., & Mallahi, H. (2019). Multimodal pedagogies in teaching english for specific purposes in higher education: Perceptions, challenges and strategies. *International Journal on Studies in Education*, 1(1), 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijonse.3>
- Lachica, F. (2023). Classroom to class zoom: Lived realities in teaching english as a second language in the philippine context. *Global Journal Al Thaqafah*. <https://doi.org/10.7187/gjat122023-1>
- Lajoie, C., Poleksic, J., Bracken-Roche, D., MacDonald, M. E., & Racine, E. (2020). The concept of vulnerability in mental health research: A mixed methods study on researcher perspectives. *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 15(3), 128–142. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264620902657>
- Lata, P., & Bhatnagar, S. (2023). Project-based learning with or without multimodal features: Action-based research for developing and assessing intercultural competence. *European Journal of Teaching and Education*, 5(2), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.33422/ejte.v5i2.102>
- Lee, Y.-F., & Lee, L.-S. (Eds.). (2023). *Trends and issues of promoting digital learning in high-digital-competitiveness countries: Country reports and international comparison* [ERIC No. ED636595]. Technological; Vocational Education Research Center, National Taiwan Normal University & K-12 Education Administration, Ministry of Education, Taiwan. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED636595.pdf>
- Lim, F. V., & Tan-Chia, L. (2023). *Designing learning for multimodal literacy: Teaching viewing and representing*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003258513>
- Lin, C.-H., & Chang, Y.-Y. (2021). A progressive digital narrative teaching method to improve learning motivation as a lifelong learning skill. *Sustainability*, 13(23), 12991. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132312991>
- Linder, R., & Ross, F. (2024). Multimodal resources and approaches for teaching young adolescents: A review of the literature. *Education Sciences*, 14(9), 1010. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14091010>
- López, P., Torrance, M., & Fidalgo, R. (2019). The online management of writing processes and their contribution to text quality in upper-primary students. *Psicothema*, 31(3), 311–318. <https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2018.326>
- Mathews, B. (2023). Adolescent capacity to consent to participate in research: A review and analysis informed by law, human rights, ethics, and developmental science. *Laws*, 12(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws12010002>
- Mazzocco, M., & Wu, X. (2021). The role of digital technology in teaching literature: Fostering collaboration and critical engagement. *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1097/DBP.0b013e31817ae8>
- McLeod, S. (2024, June). Phenomenology in qualitative research. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.225457.90725>
- Mocănașu, D. R. (2020). Determining the sample size in qualitative research. *Proceedings of the International Multidisciplinary Scientific Conference on the Dialogue between Sciences Arts, Religion Education (MCDSARE 2020)*, 181–187. <https://doi.org/10.26520/mcdsare.2020.4.181.187>
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., & King, N. (2021). Paul colaizzi’s descriptive phenomenological methodology. In *Introduction to phenomenology: Focus on methodology* (pp. 19–30). <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781071909669.n8>

- Naji, J., Subramaniam, G., & White, G. (2019). Literature and multimodality. In *New approaches to literature for language learning*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15256-7_7
- National Privacy Commission. (2022, September). Npc 21-167 maf v. shopee philippines, inc. decision. <https://www.collegesidekick.com/study-docs/6633851>
- Neubauer, B. E., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 8(2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-019-0509-2>
- Nguyen, L., Tomy, S., & Pardede, E. (2024). Enhancing collaborative learning and e-mentoring in a smart education system in higher education. *Computers*, 13(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers13010028>
- Noroozi, O., Pijera-Diaz, H., Sobocinski, M., Dindar, M., Järvelä, S., & Kirschner, P. (2020). Multimodal data indicators for capturing cognitive, motivational, and emotional learning processes: A systematic literature review. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10229-w>
- Ouzzine, A., Erguig, R., & Boudlal, A. (2022). Discovery based teaching methodology: A framework for quality teaching and learning. *Journal of Applied Language and Culture Studies*, 5, 9–27. <https://doi.org/10.2605-7506/jalcs.v5i5.29610>
- Owusu Sarfo, J., Debrah, T. P., Gbórdzoe, N. I., Afful, W. T., & Obeng, P. (2021). Qualitative research designs, sample size and saturation: Is enough always enough? *Journal of Advocacy, Research and Education*, 8(3), 60–86. <https://doi.org/10.13187/jare.2021.3.60>
- Palioura, M., & Dimoulas, C. (2022). Digital storytelling in education: A transmedia integration approach for the non-developers. *Education Sciences*, 12(8), 559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12080559>
- Pan, Y., & Zhang, L. (2021). Roles of artificial intelligence in construction engineering and management: A critical review and future trends. *Automation in Construction*, 122, 103517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103517>
- Panel on Research Ethics. (2022). Tri-council policy statement: Ethical conduct for research involving humans (tcps 2, 2022) – chapter 5: Privacy and confidentiality [Retrieved [your access date], from Government of Canada]. https://www.ger.ethique.gc.ca/eng/tcps2-epctc2_2022_chapter5-chapitre5.html
- Peddle, M. (2022). Maintaining reflexivity in qualitative nursing research. *Nursing Open*, 9(6), 2908–2914. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.999>
- Pew Research Center. (2022). The state of digital divide in education. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2022/10/01/the-digital-divide-in-education/>
- Poucher, Z. A., Tamminen, K. A., Caron, J. G., & Sweet, S. N. (2019). Thinking through and designing qualitative research studies: A focused mapping review of 30 years of qualitative research in sport psychology. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 13(1), 163–186. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1750984X.2019.1656276>
- Purtanto, C. A., Wahyuningtiyas, R. T., & Rohmana, W. I. M. (2023). Challenges in teaching english literature: A teacher’s perspective. *Jurnal JOEPALLT (Journal of English Pedagogy, Linguistics, Literature, and Teaching)*, 11(1), 59–65. <https://doi.org/10.35194/jj.v11i1.2773>

- Rafiq, S., Iqbal, S., & Afzal, D. (2023). The impact of digital tools and online learning platforms on higher education learning outcomes. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380734414>
- Red Rover. (2025, March). The role of coaching mentorship in teacher retention (and recruitment). <https://www.redroverk12.com/blog/the-role-of-coaching-mentorship-in-teacher-retention-and-recruitment>
- Resnik, D. (2020). What is ethics in research and why is it important? <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/resources/bioethics/whatis/index.cfm>
- Reyes, A. M., & Cruz, J. L. (2022). Enhancing literary appreciation through a multimodal curriculum: A study on filipino students. *Journal of Philippine Education Research*, 15(3), 34. <https://doi.org/10.56899/150.03.34>
- Rochma, A. F. (2025). Rhetorical analysis in scholarly texts: Insights into introduction and literature review patterns. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language*, 15(1), 317–341. <https://doi.org/10.23971/jefl.v15i1.9095>
- Sakulprasertsri, K. (2020). Teachers’ integration of multimodality into 21st century efl classrooms in thailand: Practice and perception. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 13(2), 225–242.
- Salinas, M. E. (2020). *Exploring the multimodal approach in teaching mindanao literature: Engaging students through diverse media* (tech. rep.). ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1292720.pdf>
- Samat, A. (2024). *The effectiveness of multimedia learning in enhancing reading* (tech. rep.). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1265894.pdf>
- Shaheen, M., Pradhan, S., & Ranajee. (2019). Sampling in qualitative research. In *Qualitative techniques for workplace data analysis* (pp. 25–51). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5366-3.ch002>
- Shorey, S., & Ng, E. D. (2022). Examining characteristics of descriptive phenomenological nursing studies: A scoping review. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 78(7), 1968–1979. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15244>
- Sibanda, S. B. (2024). Self-object relational trauma in black south african national defence force soldiers’ families: A study of secondary to persistent combat-related complex post-traumatic stress disorder. *African Journal of Sociology, Psychology and Rural Studies*, 4(2), 53–73. <https://doi.org/10.31920/2752-6585/2024/v4n2a3>
- Sinfield, G., Goldspink, S., & Wilson, C. (2023). Waiting in the wings: The enactment of a descriptive phenomenology study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069231207012>
- Sirris, S. (2022). Researchers’ role reflexivity when studying values work. In G. Espedal, B. J. Løvaas, S. Sirris, & A. Wæraas (Eds.), *Researching values: Methodological approaches for understanding values work in organisations and leadership* (pp. 205–224). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90769-3_12
- Smith, B. E., Amgott, N., & Malova, I. (2022). ”it made me think in a different way”: Bilingual students’ perspectives on multimodal composing in the english language arts classroom. *TESOL Quarterly*, 56(2), 525–551. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.3064>
- Subedi, K. R. (2021). Determining the sample in qualitative research. *Scholars’ Journal*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3126/scholars.v4i1.42457>

- Susanti, R., Saha, S., & Mallya, D. (2024). Exploring pedagogical approaches for teaching english to generation z: A bibliometric analysis. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 50(5), 442–451. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2024/v50i51374>
- Sutrisno, D., Abidin, N. A. Z., Pambudi, N., Adyawati, E., & Sallu, S. (2023). Exploring the benefits of multimodal literacy in english teaching: Engaging students through visual, auditory, and digital modes. *Global Synthesis in Education Journal*, 1(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.61667/xh184f41>
- Suwastini, N. K. A., Rinawati, N. K. A., Jayantini, I. G. A. S. R., & Dantes, G. R. (2021). Differentiated instruction for efl classroom: A conceptual review. *TELL-US Journal*, 7(1), 14–41. <https://doi.org/10.22202/tus.2021.v7i1.4719>
- Tavakol, M., & Sandars, J. (2025). Twelve tips for using phenomenology as a qualitative research approach in health professions education. *Medical Teacher*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2025.2478871>
- Tunstall, J., Saplan, K., & Stoiber, A. (2022). Qualitative research as the co construction of knowledge: Designed and emergent opportunities for equity in data collection. *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference of the Learning Sciences (ICLS 2022)*.
- Van Rijssel, T. I., van Thiel, G. J. M. W., Gardarsdottir, H., van Delden, J. J. M., & on behalf of the Trials@Home consortium. (2025). Which benefits can justify risks in research? *American Journal of Bioethics*, 25(5), 65–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15265161.2023.2296404>
- Varanasi, R. A., Vashistha, A., & Dell, N. (2024). Saharaline: A collective social support intervention for teachers in low-income indian schools. *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642617>
- Vasileiou, K., Barnett, J., Thorpe, S., & Young, T. (2018). Characterizing and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: Systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7>
- Von Gillern, S., & Stuft, C. (2022). Multimodality, learning and decision-making: Children’s metacognitive reflections on their engagement with video games as interactive texts. *Literacy*, 57(1), 3–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lit.12304>
- Walsh, M. (2019). Multimodal literacy: New approaches and perspectives. In S. Carney & M. O’Neill (Eds.), *Transforming language and literacy education* (pp. 57–74). Routledge.
- Wellington, J. (2015). *Educational research*. Bloomsbury Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781474236966>
- Wirihana, L., Welch, A., Williamson, M., Christensen, M., Bakon, S., & Craft, J. (2018). Using colaizzi’s method of data analysis to explore the experiences of nurse academics teaching on satellite campuses. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), 30–34. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2018.e1516>
- Zenouzagh, M. Z., Admiraal, W., & Saab, N. (2023). Learner autonomy, learner engagement and learner satisfaction in text-based and multimodal computer mediated writing environments. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(11), 14283–14323. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11615-w>
- Zhang, X., & Zhang, Y. (2023). An empirical study of a smart education model enabled by the edumetaverse to enhance better learning outcomes for students. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 11(2), 75. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc11020075>

- Zhao, Y. (2020). Culturally relevant pedagogy in literature classrooms: Enhancing student engagement and understanding [Preprint or unpublished manuscript].
- Žukauskas, P., Vveinhardt, J., & Andriukaitienė, R. (2018). Research ethics. In *Management culture and corporate social responsibility*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.70629>